

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH ANIMAL IDIOMS IN ENGLISH, INDONESIAN, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK ACROSS CULTURES.

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Abstract

This study deals with the analysis of phraseological units in different languages like English, Russian, Uzbek and Indonesian languages. This study is aimed to analyze the differences and similarities of phraseological units with animal idioms. The researcher works with the phraseological units with animal idioms which shared by all and partially in four languages.

Key words: phraseological units, animal idioms, semantic meanings

Culturally-loaded vocabulary plays an important role in a language. Different social backgrounds, history, and national culture have a great effect on cultural connotations. As to animal idioms, culture exerts an important influence on these expressions, such as geographical culture, historical culture, customary culture, religious culture, literary works, myth, legends, and fables. With comparison, the same animal words may bear the same and different cultural meanings. And different animal words may convey the similar or even same meaning.

The idiom composed of an animal noun phrase in English, Russian, Indonesian and Uzbek cultures is an outstanding cultural phenomenon. Some of the animal idioms have similar cultural meanings, while some others are a very different or have subtle differences from each other. The meaning of an animal idiom depends on what images the animal stands for in three different cultures. Some animals stand for similar images in languages, such as the fox, while some stand for greatly different or subtle different images, such as the dog.

Animal idioms get their established connotations in these languages. People associate their feelings and emotions, even happiness and natural phenomena, with various animals, which are thought to represent different characters, like people, or serve as omens. Many animals have become a kind of symbol in people's thinking, and their symbolism is reflected in the language. Therefore, similarities and differences in the connotations of animal idiom in these languages should be taken into consideration in cross-cultural communication and translation. There are various factors affecting the similarities and differences in the connotations of animal idioms in three languages. One of them is the geographical differences. Geography is closely relative to the formation and development of culture. Every culture is formed by its unique geography and climate

Between language and culture, there are many mutual influences. Since the environment where human beings live have something in common, there are many animal idioms that possess similar cultural metaphor of the same animal. The similarities between English, Russian, Indonesia, and Uzbek people have been mirrored in the sphere of life experience and understanding of common. In this case, English, Indonesian, and Uzbek people

have the same association, assigning animal idioms same connotation of cultural metaphor. We look at the following example:

Parrot

It is universally known that parrot is good at imitating human language or blindly repeat what people uttered. Consequently, it is used to refer to a person without his own opinion in both Uzbek and English, which can be proved by Uzbek idiom to'tiqushdek takrorlamoq and the verbalized "parrot"

- Wolf

In English, Russian, Indonesia, and Uzbek cultures, people believe that wolf has a cunning, greedy and cruel nature and use to compare wolf to greedy, murderous people. In these countries, idiom stating wolf in sheep's clothing (in Russian: волк в овечьей шкуре, in Indonesian: serigala berbulu dumba, in Uzbek: qo'y terisini yopinib olgan bo'ri) is used to cynically imply who looks nice but is ruthless in fact.

- Donkey

Like wolf, donkey is seen by people of English, Russian, Indonesia, and Uzbek as animal that is stubborn, stupid and inflexible. Indonesian people even consider donkey as a lazy animal. So, when we compare donkey with a person, it means that this person is lazy, stubborn or inflexible. English, Russian and Uzbek people have idiom for donkey, which is stubborn as a mule/donkey in English, упрямый как осёл in Russian, eshakday qaysar in Uzbek which means a person who is obstinate like a mule or donkey.

- Monkey

This animal has also same connotation for English, Russian, Indonesian, and Uzbek people which is used to describe someone as stupid. There is an idiom about monkey like make a monkey out of someone in English, сделать из себя мартышку in Russian means to make someone foolish or to make someone appear stupid.

Lamb

Lamb is a good case in point. Lamb can stand for tameness and obedience. Like a lamb means doing something obediently while expression like qoy'dek is also available in Uzbek and как ягненок /агнец in Russian. In addition to the connotation of "tameness", lamb bears important religious connotations_ the follower of the God and the vulnerable. But to a language that was not affected so much by Christianity. As we know English, Russian, Indonesian, and Uzbek people live in different geographical environment, customs, religion, and other aspects; the language which can reflect the culture is also different. Customs are an important part in culture, clearly reflecting the lifestyle and standard of thinking of national people. People have different customs when they live in different societies. Affected by different customs, people from different nations have different attitudes towards the same animal. English, Indonesia, and Uzbek people are originated from different ethnic and geography. Consequently, they have their own unique meanings of the same animal. We can take a look at the following example:

- Dog

For English people, this animal is considered to have a positive association. Dog is man's best friend. It always accompany human wherever and whenever they are. Dog always does what its master commands. Many people regard the dogs as their best friends and important members in their families. They spend much money buying dog toys and food. They

hold and attend the funerals for dogs. There are many facilities specially designed for dogs because of people's faithful feeling to dogs, such as pet shops, pet restaurants, beauty parlors for dogs, and so on. What is more impressive is that they feel what the dogs feel. They will be very sad when the dogs are sick or dead. In most cases, the word "dog" is neutral in its connotation in the English language. It is all right to refer to certain people as big dog, top dog, lucky dog, in English. To help a lame dog over the stile means "to help someone in difficulty". To let a sleeping dog lie means "to make no trouble" or "not to disturb people." Every dog has its day means "every person will someday succeed or become fortunate."

Nowadays, there is still much news about how the dogs save people who are in danger. The dog is the animal who can understand people's emotions. The dog genuinely plays an important role in English speaking people's life.

The association of dog will be different when it comes to Indonesian and Uzbek people. Shortly, dog has negative association. Dogs have been tamed to be doorkeepers for a long time. In ancient times, the reason people kept dogs was that they need a faithful animal to look after their houses and property. Affected by Western culture, people start to show more affection to dogs gradually. However, most Uzbek idioms formed by the word "dog" are with derogatory connotation. Most their meaning are about despicable and hatred. With a strong sense of being negative, Uzbek give the dog "servility". It is commonly used to describe the bad people and bad things. Oriental culture pays attention to the negative characteristics of dogs. Everything relating to ugly words is given to this animal in order to express humanity disgust and contempt. The idiom with the dog in Uzbek itning kunini kormoq, means living like a dog in a bad condition.

One of the factors causing such negative perspective about a dog is due to Islamic religion rules. Islam forbid people to get close or even touch a dog because it can cause someone's physical body to be an excretion. If moslem people's body is in excretion, then, they are not allowed to take a prayer (sholat). Shortly, for these countries, especially for moslem people who are the dominant in these countries, dog is kind of an animal you do not want to deal with or even to touch.

Indonesian and Uzbek people have idioms for this animal, which is it mushukday yashamoq and seperti anjing dan kucing. In English, this idiom can be stated as to fight like cat and dog and in Russian жить как кошка с собакой. It means constantly quarelling in constant conflict with each other.

- Fish

For English and Indonesian people, fish is kind of animal that you want to deal with. People of these countries really love this animal. English and Indonesia have something in common. Both countries are surrounded by sea. Because of this factor, fishing and farming which originated from its unique geographical location and natural conditions also have an important influence on English and Indonesia. As a result, their languages are closely relative to the ocean and commerce. So are the idioms. There are many fish-related idioms in these countries. Fish often refer to a person. The British use fish to represent all kinds of people: a big fish (a tycoon) or a queer fish (a strange or crazy person). For example, when someone is described as a cool fish, it usually means he is very grim. When people say a fish out of water, they are referring to a person who feels uncomfortable or awkward because he or she is in surroundings that are not familiar. When people say he or she has bigger or other fish to fry, it means he or she has more important or more interesting things to do. The idiom as mute as

fish vividly pictures a silent person who talks little. Besides, drink like a fish means drinking too much alcohol, never offer to teach a fish to swim means do not show off your knowledge before the professional people. There are plenty more fish in the sea means that there are many other people or things that are as good as the one somebody has failed to get. The best fish swim near the bottom means the best thing is near the bottom.

The analysis of the semantic meanings of the phraseological elements associated with animal expressions in these four languages showed that, so as to give the exact meaning, each phrase should be related to contextual meaning. These vibrant expressions have their own unique connotative meanings, which serve our speech by making it easier for our live communication. In conclusion, we can consider that all languages have similarities and differences in meanings and use phraseological units with animal idioms based on their cultural background.

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